

Table S2. Univariate mixed-effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* mutations in *P. falciparum* positive samples

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented of univariate models (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effect(s)	Samples	N51				C59				S108				triple <i>dhfr</i>			
		OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (per 10 years)	ANC	0.59	0.42	0.84	0.004	0.70	0.48	1.01	0.058	0.78	0.54	1.15	0.213	0.61	0.43	0.86	0.005
	Del	1.32	0.80	2.17	0.279	1.75	0.92	3.33	0.087	2.30	1.09	4.83	0.028	1.32	0.81	2.15	0.265
	GP	1.01	0.86	1.18	0.949	0.89	0.76	1.05	0.175	0.85	0.72	1.02	0.079	1.03	0.88	1.20	0.729
Parasitaemia (log scale)	ANC	1.20	0.95	1.53	0.133	1.01	0.78	1.30	0.965	1.02	0.79	1.33	0.859	1.20	0.94	1.52	0.136
	Del	0.80	0.61	1.03	0.086	0.84	0.61	1.15	0.280	0.72	0.51	1.03	0.073	0.83	0.64	1.07	0.154
	GP	1.16	0.89	1.52	0.270	1.17	0.88	1.57	0.278	1.27	0.92	1.75	0.148	1.15	0.90	1.49	0.269
Gravidity	ANC	0.92	0.83	1.02	0.100	0.93	0.84	1.04	0.212	0.97	0.86	1.08	0.569	0.91	0.82	1.01	0.075
	Del	1.20	1.03	1.41	0.021	1.27	1.04	1.56	0.020	1.39	1.09	1.77	0.009	1.20	1.03	1.40	0.019
Season#	ANC	1.00	0.66	1.52	0.990	1.01	0.64	1.57	0.975	1.00	0.63	1.59	0.994	0.98	0.65	1.48	0.926
	Del	3.98	1.67	9.53	0.002	4.98	1.86	13.37	0.001	5.42	2.05	14.29	0.001	4.37	1.77	10.8	0.001
SP doses	Del	1.01	0.71	1.42	0.966	1.26	0.80	2.00	0.320	1.41	0.83	2.41	0.204	0.97	0.88	0.70	0.881
AL	Del	0.33	0.17	0.64	0.001	0.59	0.27	1.30	0.190	0.61	0.26	1.45	0.268	0.37	0.19	0.70	0.002
Visit	ANC & Del*	1.54	0.97	2.47	0.069	2.09	1.17	3.75	0.013	2.64	1.20	5.81	0.016	1.52	1.04	2.21	0.029
	ANC & GP**	1.93	1.39	2.68	0.000	1.95	1.37	2.79	0.000	2.22	1.52	3.25	0.000	1.79	1.30	2.45	0.000
	GP & Del***	0.76	0.50	1.15	0.201	1.02	0.63	1.64	0.950	1.01	0.60	1.70	0.980	0.84	0.56	1.26	0.394

<i>dhps</i> Fixed effect(s)	Samples	S436				A437			
		OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (per 10 years)	ANC	1.08	0.73	1.60	0.696	0.79	0.52	1.19	0.266
	Del	1.12	0.67	1.87	0.653	0.68	0.31	1.48	0.325
	GP	0.86	0.75	0.99	0.042	0.91	0.77	1.08	0.284
Parasitaemia (log scale)	ANC	1.31	1.00	1.72	0.052	1.13	0.84	1.52	0.429
	Del	1.04	0.80	1.36	0.753	0.85	0.59	1.23	0.395
	GP	1.18	0.90	1.53	0.229	1.35	0.98	1.84	0.062
Gravidity	ANC	0.97	0.87	1.08	0.583	0.95	0.84	1.07	0.418
	Del	1.05	0.90	1.22	0.563	0.92	0.73	1.15	0.453
Season#	ANC	1.47	0.92	2.36	0.109	0.71	0.42	1.18	0.184
	Del	2.05	0.84	4.99	0.113	1.52	0.43	5.38	0.518
SP doses	Del	0.97	0.69	1.36	0.848	1.43	0.81	2.53	0.216
AL	Del	0.73	0.37	1.43	0.357	0.44	0.17	1.12	0.085
Visit	ANC & Del*	1.06	0.64	1.75	0.823	1.72	1.03	2.85	0.037
	ANC & GP**	1.57	1.11	2.23	0.010	1.44	0.98	2.12	0.066
	GP & Del***	0.69	0.46	1.05	0.086	1.17	0.68	2.01	0.568

AL = artemether-lumefantrine therapy; Del = delivery; # low transmission season = 0, high transmission season = 1; *ANC booking = 0, Delivery = 1; **ANC booking = 0, GP = 1; *** GP = 0, Del = 1

